

Medicinal and Bioactive Properties of Genus *Achillea*: Recent Updates

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Abstract

The genus *Achillea* is a member of Family Asteraceae and includes over 130 flowering perennial species, holds an important place in traditional and recent herbal medicine. *Achillea* is noteworthy for its extensive application across ethnomedicinal systems, especially in European and Indian Unani medicine. The plant has rich source of bioactive compounds, like flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, essential oils, and sesquiterpenes, with a number of therapeutic benefits. This review explores the phytochemical compositions and therapeutic properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, gastrointestinal protective, hemostatic, antidiabetic, and anticancer properties of this genus.

Keywords

Achillea, Phytochemicals, Pharmacological Activity, Phenolic Compounds.

Introduction

The ancient conventional knowledge of medicinal plants is the principle on which medications have been formulated since the earliest days of human civilization. The potential for medicine creation appears to be unlimited when this ancient knowledge is combined with fresh techniques drawn from modern research. As a result, ethnopharmacology has developed substantially, with many research papers being published every year (Barda et al., 2021). About 140 perennial plants that are common to the Northern Hemisphere belong to the genus *Achillea*. Traditional Indian medicine, especially Unani medicine, incorporates use of the *Achillea* species (Bano, 2018; Nemeth & Bernath, 2008).

Achillea (Yarrow) is a member of the largest group of vascular plants, the Asteraceae (Compositae). Although they can be observed all throughout the world, asteraceaeous plants are more common in dry and semi-arid regions of lower temperate and subtropical latitudes. There are over 130 flowering and perennial species in the *Achillea* genus, which is found in temperate regions of Asia and Europe. A few species are additionally found in North America. Usually, these plants contain flat clusters of tiny flowers on top of the stem, alongside hairy, aromatic leaves. Many types of these flowers are common garden plants because of their diverse colouration. The name *Achillea* refers to Achilles, who treated the wounds of soldiers who fought Iliadic Trojan War with the application of yarrow. The various aspects of *Achillea* as a remarkable and therapeutic genus are not extensively addressed in review publications (Saeidnia et al., 2011).

Plants often have rhizomes and one to four clustered stems. Groups 3 to 8 of the the flowers are grouped together on tiny discs and are typically white to pink in colour. The lowest leaves are typically larger, and the leaves are visible down the stem. The hair-covered leaves can grow up to 20 cm in length. *Achillea* is pollinated specifically by insects. *Achillea* is regenerated by the seeds. For germination, seeds require temperatures between 18 and 24°C and direct sunlight. Although there is an extensive amount of morphological variability, the flowers' morphology and structure show a lesser degree of variation (Salehi et al., 2020). In India *Achillea* commonly occur at altitudes between 1050 and 3600 meters in the regions of Himalaya, from Kashmir to Kumaun. There have also been instances of it growing wild in Belgaum and Bombay. The herb usually grow in the month of May and June (Shawl et al., 2002).

Objective of study

This review paper explores the phytochemical compositions and therapeutic properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, gastrointestinal protective, hemostatic, antidiabetic, and anticancer properties of this genus.

Review of Literature

The aerial parts and flowering tops are the most medicinally useful parts of yarrow. Yarrow has long been used in European traditional medicine because it contains flavonoids that help with digestion, ease stomach and menstrual cramps, and treat hay fever and other allergic mucous disorders. Essential oils, with a potent anti-inflammatory activity, commonly used to massage chest in flu and colds. Leaves are placed on nosebleeds to aid with clotting. Aerial parts improve circulation, reduce blood pressure, promote bile flow, and function as a digestive tonic. In addition, yarrow is used as a diuretic, blood purifier, immune-boosting agent, and treatment for fevers, infections, skin disorders, and irregular menstruation (Lakshmi et al., 2011).

When compared to other plant species, *Achillea* spp. seem to be especially rich in a number of secondary metabolites. Glycosylated and nonglycosylated flavonoids, phenolic acids (mostly derivatives of benzoic acids and cinnamic), terpenes (including diterpens, guaianolides, sesquiterpenes, and their oxygenated forms), phytosterols, fatty acids, organic acids, and alcohols are among the most common natural compounds. The existence of several natural compounds might be responsible for the diverse biological activity of *Achillea* species. Several in vitro and in vivo researches have confirmed traditional applications of *Achillea* and established it as an herb with multiple medicinal benefits. A few of the notable medicinal activity of extracts of *Achillea* spp are Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antihemorrhagic, wound healing, skin soothing, skin rejuvenation, anxiolytic, anticancer, antispasmodic, hepatoprotective, oestrogenic, cytotoxic, and choleric activity (Orhan, 2019; Strzypek-Gomółka et al., 2021).

A table of different species of *Achillea* with its diverse compounds, medicinal properties, traditional use and common name is given to show the pharmacological activities (Table 1).

Main Text**Phytochemical Composition**

According to phytochemical studies of these plants, numerous components from the genus *Achillea* are extremely bioactive. *Achillea* species have been found to include flavonoids, terpenoids, lignans, fatty acids, amino acid derivatives, and alkaloids including p-hydroxyphenethylamide IV, according to the literature search (Saeidnia et al., 2011)

Pharmacological Activity of *Achillea* species

The pharmacological characteristics of species in the *Achillea* genus include antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, antioxidant, antispasmodic, anti-diabetic, anti-ulcer, antitumor, choleric, and hepatoprotective effects (Fig.1).

Table 1. Important medicinal properties of genus *Achillea*.

S. No.	Species Name	Common Name	Region	Traditional Uses	Class of Compound	Biological Role	Ref
1.	<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	Yarrow	Europe, western Asia, and North America	Management of stomach related problems like bleeding. Menstrual cycle related pains issues; Problems related with gastrointestinal tracts, urinary tract, skin, respiratory tract issues.	Monoterpenoid, Terpenoid, Ketones, Flavonoid, Polyols, Estrogenic Flavonoid, Phenolic Glycoside, Alkaloids	Anti-inflammatory, reducing triglyceride level, antibacterial, anti-tumour, antioxidant, neuroprotective, Decrease anxiety, sedative effects, hepatoprotective, dermal sensitizer, Antitussive, analgesic, nasal decongestant,	(Barda et al., 2021; Farasati Far et al., 2023)
2.	<i>Achillea filipendulina</i>	Fernleaf yarrow	Afghanistan, Iraq, Pakistan, Iran, Turkey, Kazakhstan and the Caucasus	Hypoglycaemia Joint related problem, heart related problems, stomach and intestinal problems, uric acid accumulation as in gout, for management of protozoan disease such as malaria, and purgative agent	Alkaloid, Flavonoid, Terpenoid, Glycosidic, Steroidal, Saponin and Tannins	Anti-inflammatory and antiseptic, antioxidant, antimalarial, anti-gout	(Asnaashari et al., 2023; Barda et al., 2021)
3.	<i>Achillea tenorii</i>	Tenore's yarrow	Mountains of central and southern Apennines	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and wound-healing properties, gastrointestinal issues, hemorrhages, and menstrual problems	Flavonoids And Phenolic Acids	Antioxidant activity,	(Venditti et al., 2015)
4.	<i>Achillea ageratum</i>	Sweet Yarrow	Morocco	Stomach and gastrointestinal disorders, cytostatic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic activities	Germacrane-And Elemene-Type Alcohols, Ketones, Acetates of The Artemisyl Group, and Flavonoids	Stomach, gastrointestinal disorders, cytostatic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic activities	(El Bouzidi et al., 2012; Mohammadhosseini et al., 2017)
5.	<i>Achillea atrata</i>	Tea	Serbia	Tonic and for bronchial and laryngeal troubles	Flavonoids Aglycones	Antifungal activity	(Ristić et al., 2004)

Antioxidant Activity

In addition to protecting the lipids from oxidation, antioxidants may also have health benefits by preventing the degradation of cells. Natural compounds derived from *Achillea* species help prevent chronic illnesses by lowering the oxidative damage triggered on by extremely reactive substances like reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Gharibi et al., 2013).

Anti-inflammatory Activity

Essential oils from *Achillea* are abundant in oxygenated volatile molecules that have anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. Terpenoids, aliphatic, and aromatic chemicals make up the majority of the complex, hydrophobic mixture of organic volatile components, that constitute essential oils. The anti-inflammatory properties of essential oils are attributed to these constituents (Tawfik et al., 2024).

Antimicrobial Properties

Several constituents like essential oils, sesquiterpenes, phenolic compounds, and other chemical components are responsible for pharmacological activities of this genus. Specifically, it has been suggested that its antibacterial activities are attributed to the presence of several secondary metabolites, including flavonoids and phenols (Grigore et al., 2020).

Gastrointestinal Benefits

With over a hundred species, the *Achillea* genus has demonstrated a wide range of applications in traditional medicine for many diseases including rheumatic pain, pneumonia, haemorrhage, wound, gastrointestinal and hepatobiliary disorders. Potrich et al. (2010) examined gastroprotective properties of hydroalcoholic extract of *A. millefolium*. In their study, ethanol was used to cause acute gastric lesions and acetic acid to induce persistent stomach ulcers. Lesser development of the lesion area was observed in the test animal after pretreatment with *Achillea* extract. Additionally, when the plant extract was given orally, the levels of SOD (superoxide dismutase) and glutathione (GSH) increased with simultaneous reduction in myeloperoxidase (MPO) activity. These alterations in the antioxidant enzymes were associated with the

antiulcerogenic activity of the plant extract. Hepatoprotective properties of the *Achillea* extracts has also been documented in different drug induced hepatitis in mice models (Dabbaghi et al., 2025).

Hemostatic Activity

One common and serious surgical consequence is bleeding. In every surgical treatment, reducing blood loss is a crucial concern. Achieving haemostasis quickly has several advantages, including improved haemodynamic stability and a reduction in the risk of blood transfusion-related side effects such as infections and allergic responses. *Achillea* has long been used to prevent internal bleeding. Research has demonstrated that a hydroalcoholic extract of *Achillea millefolium*'s flowering aerial parts is effective in preventing bleeding in specific locations (Bagheri et al., 2024).

Anticancer Activity

Achillea species are being used to treat a number of diseases, including gout, digestive problems, arthritis, sciatica, malaria, and heart disease. They are also evidenced to have antioxidant, antibacterial, antidiabetic, and wound-healing effects. Anticancer activity of *Achillea filipendulina* has been investigated in breast cancer cell lines (Tunç et al., 2024).

Figure 1. Medicinal Properties of genus *Achillea*

Antidiabetic Activity

Phytochemical of this genus have demonstrated extensive health benefits in chronic diseases such as diabetes, inflammation, and diabetic neuropathy pain. *Achillea millefolium* is also utilised to treat diabetes and related conditions in various regions of the Globe (Chávez-Silva et al., 2018).

Conclusion

Achillea is a remarkable genus of medicinal herbs with an established ethnobotanical history and therapeutic potential backed by modern science. Numerous pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, antidiabetic, and antioxidant activity, are attributed to the presence of a variety of phytochemical. Traditional use of its various parts specially its aerial parts match with current research. This match confirms its application in the treatment of heart disease, Skin problems, and gastrointestinal disorders. New and standard formulations of natural components from the plants and its standardized therapeutic uses can be further established by ongoing phytopharmacological research. *Achillea* offers promising opportunities for the development of natural therapies and integrative healthcare solutions in the context of the increased interest in plant-based medicine.

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Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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